

ECO-FRIENDLY CLEANSING MILK FORMULATION USING JOJOBA AND BLACK SEED OIL IN SELF-EMULSIFYING MICROEMULSION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The need for natural and sustainable personal and skin care products has enabled novel formulations to develop that respond to the dual concerns of efficacy and skin acceptability. The goal of this study was to develop and study a new self-emulsifying micro-emulsion cleansing milk formulation containing natural active ingredients, Jojoba oil and Black seed oil. Two oil blends were prepared: Blend A (jojoba: black seed oil, 90:10 w/w) and Blend B (80:20 w/w). Both formulations used PEG-40 hydrogenated castor oil (HLB 13.1) as the emulsifier. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were created in an effort to identify the stable micro-emulsion region. The Physicochemical characterization consisted of droplet size, pH, conductivity and stability. Results indicated that both oil blends produced stable micro-emulsions (74.2 - 189.7 nm) with good droplet dispersion. Blend A was more efficient at

forming micro-emulsions and stability than blend B as it formed mostly oil in water (O/W) micro-emulsions with smaller droplet sizes (90.5 and 101.4 nm), higher conductivity (234.1 and 334.2 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). All formulations were stable to thermodynamic testing. The final cleansing milk formulations had an appropriate viscosity (515.5 - 698.9 cps), skin compatible pH (6.5-6.8), and all formulations were homogeneous. This research successfully demonstrates the feasibility of combining natural oils with self-emulsifying micro-emulsion technology to create stable, effective, and environmentally friendly cosmetic cleansing products that offer an alternative to conventional synthetic formulations.

KEYWORDS: Jojoba oil, black seed oil, cleansing milk, natural cosmetics, skincare formulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global skincare market is experiencing a significant shift from conventional to natural and sustainable cosmetic products. This trend is resulting from an increase in consumer awareness regarding artificial chemicals and ingredients and their impact on the environment. Facial cleansers are among the most common types of cosmetic products used in people's daily skincare routines. Cleansers must remove impurities, makeup, and oil while protecting a person's skin barrier and maintaining proper pH. Conventional or traditional cleansers, especially those made with harsh surfactants such as sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), strip the skin off its natural lipid barrier, which can lead to drying, irritation, and impaired skin barrier function. There is an important unmet need for gentle yet effective cleansing solutions to cleanse well while preserving skin health.^[1-3]

Micro-emulsions are a complicated kind of colloidal system. Micro-emulsions are stable and transparent mixtures of oil and water stabilized by surfactants and co-surfactants that are part of the formulation. Micro-emulsions also differ from typical emulsions because of their better stability, greater solubilization capacity, and enhanced penetration efficacy associated with their nano scale droplet size. These remarkable features of micro-emulsions make them attractive to cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. More accurately, the benefits of micro-emulsions provide dissolution, bioavailability, aesthetics, and extended shelf life.^[4-8]

Jojoba oil, which is classified as a liquid wax ester, is well-known for its use in cosmetic products because its molecular structure closely resembles that of human sebum. Jojoba oil is composed primarily of long-chain fatty acids and fatty alcohols, and it displays remarkable stability when air-exposed. Jojoba oil is non-comedogenic, and it is bio compatible with skin. In addition, the similarity of jojoba oil with skin lipids allows it to penetrate easily and not feel greasy, making it an ideal carrier oil for the face. Jojoba oil also has inherent antimicrobial properties.^[9-12] With respect to skincare, Black seed oil has demonstrated possible benefits in the treatment of acne and restoration of the skin barrier, as well as potential protection against aging related to oxidative stress. Including Black seed oil in cleansing products would probably be more beneficial than just providing a normal clean. Natural oil-based cosmetics are gaining popularity, though only a few studies have examined the approach of making self-emulsifying cleansing products. Self-emulsifying cleansing

products could potentially blend the benefits of micro-emulsion technology and the restorative properties of natural oils. Conventional surfactants are commonly used as the emulsifying agent in commercial cleansers but can cause damage to the skin barrier. Natural oil cleansers tend to lack cleansing capacity, which makes it difficult to completely release makeup and impurities from the skin.^[13-15]

The aim of this research is to develop and fully characterize a new cleansing milk self-emulsifying micro-emulsion system that incorporates jojoba oil and Black seed oil. This product represents a more desirable natural alternative to standard synthetic cleansing systems. The research will examine approaches to enhance the stability, cleansing efficacy and compatibility of the self-emulsifying micro-emulsion system. A main goal is to ascertain consumer satisfaction and product sustainability. Characterization of the product will focus on the micro-emulsion properties, droplet size distribution, efficiency of the self-emulsifying properties, and physical stability of the product. Overall, this research will demonstrate that naturally sourced components within a self-emulsifying micro-emulsion technology can be utilized to produce effective, stable, and aesthetically pleasing personal care products. By making use of the self-emulsifying micro-emulsion technology along with the combination of jojoba oil and Black seed oil, we are part of the increasing body of research around sustainable personal care formulations that are both health-conscious to the consumer as well as environmentally friendly. Likewise, this work will create benchmarks for sustainable formulations and the possibilities within the category of Eco-conscious cosmetics in the personal care industry.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Jojoba oil and black seed oil were obtained from Bhagavati Herbal & Health Care Pvt. Ltd. (Gujarat, India). PEG-40 hydrogenated castor oil (HLB 13.1) was Gifted from Rossari Biotech Ltd. (Mumbai, India). All other reagents and solvents were of analytical grade.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Oils and Surfactant Characterization

Jojoba oil and Black seed oil were analyzed for appearance, specific gravity, acid value, peroxide value, iodine value, and saponification value using pharmacopeial methods. PEG-40 hydrogenated castor oil was evaluated for appearance, specific gravity, and HLB value to confirm emulsifying suitability. Two oil blends were prepared:

- **Blend A:** Jojoba oil: Black seed oil (90:10, w/w)
- **Blend B:** Jojoba oil: Black seed oil (80:20, w/w)

2.2.2 Phase Diagram Construction

Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed by water titration at ambient temperature. Oil blends were mixed with PEG-40 HYDROGENATED CASTOR OIL various oil-to-surfactant ratios (0:10 to 10:0). De-ionized water was titrated drop-wise with gentle stirring until turbidity appeared. Water incorporation capacity and phase behavior were recorded to establish micro-emulsion regions. Formulations within the identified micro-emulsion zones were selected for cleansing milk preparation. These were further characterized for appearance, viscosity, pH, droplet size, and conductivity to determine their Physicochemical suitability.

2.2.3 Formulation of Cleansing Milk

Micro-emulsion systems identified within stable regions were selected for cleansing milk preparation. The formulations were then evaluated for Physicochemical characteristics and stability.

2.2.4 Characterization of Micro-emulsions

Micro-emulsions were visually inspected for clarity, homogeneity, and absence of phase separation. pH was measured at 25 ± 2 °C using a digital pH meter. Droplet size and Polydispersity index (PDI) were determined by dynamic light scattering (Malvern Mastersizer 3000 Hydro, UK). Electrical conductivity was measured to distinguish O/W from W/O systems. Stability was assessed over 30 days at room temperature by monitoring pH, viscosity, droplet size, and conductivity, along with centrifugation at 3,000 rpm for 30 min.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characterization of Jojoba Oil & Black seed Oil and their blend

Table 1: - Physicochemical parameters of oil.

Sr.no	Parameter	Jojoba Oil	Black seed Oil
1	Appearance	Pale yellow, clear	Light brownish yellow
2	Specific gravity	0.862	0.912
3	Acid value (mg KOH/g)	1.12	1.86
4	Peroxide value (meq/kg)	3.1	5.6
5	Iodine value (g I ₂ /100g)	82.4	92.8
6	Saponification value	94.6	179.2

Table 2: Physicochemical Parameters of Oil Blends.

Sr.no	Parameter	JB BLEND A Jojoba oil: Black seed oil (90:10, w/w)	JB BLEND b Jojoba oil: Black seed oil (80:20, w/w)
1	Appearance	Yellow clear liquid	Brown clear liquid
3	Odour	Mild odor	Strong odor
4	Specific gravity	0.872	0.894
5	Acid value (mg KOH/g)	1.21	1.34
6	Peroxide value (meq/kg)	3.36	3.61
7	Iodine value (g I ₂ /100g)	83.44	85.7
8	Saponification value	101.34	109.41

3.2 Characterization of Emulsifier

Table 3: - Physicochemical parameters of surfactant.

Sr.no	Parameter	PEG-40 HYDROGENATED CASTOR OIL
1	Physical appearance	Colourless to pale yellow liquid to paste.
2	Specific Gravity	1.056
3	Saponification value	58
4	Hydroxyl value	65
5	Moisture content	0.32
6	Surface tension	43.4 mN/m
8	HLB value	13.1

3.3 Construction of Phase Diagram for micro-emulsion

Micro-emulsion formulations were prepared using two oil blends: JB BLEND A (Jojoba oil: Black seed oil, 90:10 w/w) and JB BLEND B (Jojoba oil: Black seed oil, 80:20 w/w). The surfactant employed in both systems was PEG-40 Hydrogenated Castor Oil. For each system, the surfactant was mixed with the oil phase at specified ratios, followed by gradual titration with distilled water under gentle stirring to obtain stable micro-emulsions. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed for both JB BLEND A and JB BLEND B formulations. The diagrams illustrate the phase behavior of the ternary mixtures consisting of oil (JB blends), PEG-40 Hydrogenated Castor Oil, and water. The shaded regions in the diagrams represent the micro-emulsion formation zones observed at room temperature. These diagrams enable systematic evaluation of the influence of oil blend composition on the formation and stability of microemulsions in the ternary system.

Fig. 1: JB BLEND A micro-emulsion with HLB 13.1. Fig. 2: JB BLEND B micro-emulsion with HLB 13.1

Table 4: Composition of JB Blend Formulations.

Sr.no	Formulation	HLB	OIL	S _{MIX}	WATER	TOTAL
1	JB BLEND A-1	HLB 13.1	8.57	20	71.42	100
2	JB BLEND A-2	HLB 13.1	17.24	17.24	65.51	100
3	JB BLEND A-3	HLB 13.1	69.81	17.45	12.73	100
4	JB BLEND A-4	HLB 13.1	80.99	8.99	10	100
5	JB BLEND B-1	HLB 13.1	4.87	19.51	75.60	100
6	JB BLEND B-2	HLB 13.1	2.94	6.86	90.19	100
7	JB BLEND B-3	HLB 13.1	40.61	17.40	41.97	100
8	JB BLEND B-4	HLB 13.1	53.33	13.33	33.33	100

Table -5: - Physicochemical Characterization of JB Blend Formulations.

Sr.no	Formulation	HLB	Type of emulsion	pH	Density	Conductivity	Particle size
1	JB BLEND A-1	HLB 13.1	O/W	6.1	1.023	234.1	90.5
2	JB BLEND A-2	HLB 13.1	O/W	6.23	1.013	334.2	101.4
3	JB BLEND A-3	HLB 13.1	W/O	6.34	1.014	45.2	140.9
4	JB BLEND A-4	HLB 13.1	W/O	6.15	1.012	55.3	173.8
5	JB BLEND B-1	HLB 13.1	O/W	6.2	1.013	254.5	74.2
6	JB BLEND B-2	HLB 13.1	O/W	6.54	1.014	314.3	93.1
7	JB BLEND B-3	HLB 13.1	W/O	6.54	1.016	45.5	151.1
8	JB BLEND B-4	HLB 13.1	W/O	6.54	1.014	58.9	189.7

Table -6: - Microemulsion centrifuge stability data.

Sr.no	Formulation	HLB	Centrifuge stability Before	Centrifuge stability After 30 days
1	JB BLEND A-1	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
2	JB BLEND A-2	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
3	JB BLEND A-3	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
4	JB BLEND A-4	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
5	JB BLEND B-1	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
6	JB BLEND B-2	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
7	JB BLEND B-3	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable
8	JB BLEND B-4	HLB 13.1	Stable	Stable

Table 7: Microemulsion based Cleansing Milk formulation.

Sr.no	Raw Material	Formulation -1	Formulation -2
1	Xanthan gum	0.2	0.2
2	Glycerine	5	5
3	Aloe vera extract	0.5	0.5
4	Phenoxyethanols	0.5	0.5
5	Vitamin E	0.01	0.01
6	Water	62.99	62.99
7	JB BLEND A-1	30	0
8	JB BLEND B-1	0	30
		100	100

Table 8: Microemulsion based Cleansing Milk formulation physicochemical parameter.

Sr.no	Formulation	Appearance	pH	Viscosity (cps)	Centrifuge stability
1	Formulation -1	Viscous Liquid	6.5	515.5	No Separation
2	Formulation -2	Viscous Liquid	6.8	698.9	No Separation

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Oil Characterization and Blend Optimization

The results of the Physicochemical analyses of jojoba and black seed oils showed complementary attributes that substantiated the use of a combined oil in cosmetic applications. Jojoba oil had greater oxidative stability demonstrated by much lower acid (1.12 mg KOH/g) and peroxide (3.1 meq/kg) values than black seed oil. It is generally accepted that jojoba oil has a superior resistance to rancidity due to the unique wax esters that it consists of, a fact that is important when considering shelf-life and sensory (taste and smell) attributes of products. On the other hand, the black seed oil's higher iodine value (92.8 g I₂/100g) equated to a more unsaturated oil, and might be related to the reported anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant activity and health claim of the oil's bio-active which hopefully take advantage of some of the stability gained through the formulation with jojoba oil. The blend also showed that by increasing the percentage of jojoba oil (Blend A, 90:10) even higher overall stability could be achieved while still gaining some of the benefits associated with the black seed oil. This supports the idea of using jojoba oil as a stabilizing carrier for more volatile and reactive natural oils potentially extending the shelf life and integrity of other cosmetic formulations. The applicability of the concept could go beyond cosmetics, to other practices using oils that are otherwise unstable but still possess benefits that justify their use in formulations.

4.2 Micro-emulsion Formation and Phase Behavior

The successful development of pseudo-ternary phase diagrams provided evidence of the compatibility of the oil blends with PEG-40 hydrogenated castor oil, developing clear micro-emulsion forming areas. The larger micro-emulsion region, as seen with Blend A, indicates an increase in emulsification efficiency - likely due to the structural compatibility of jojoba oil to skin sebum, and a concomitant increase in interaction with the non-ionic surfactant. The transition between O/W to W/O micro-emulsions with increasing oil also follows established principles of colloid science, where phase behavior is guided by surfactant packing parameters. The O/W systems (formulations A-1, A-2, B-1, B-2) have smaller droplet sizes (74.2-101.4 nm) and greater conductivity values - both considerations confirm their potential for cleansing applications where rapid spreading and rinsing is desired.

4.3 Nanometric Droplet Size and Stability Implications

Achieving nanometric droplet sizes across all formulations is a key milestone in natural cosmetic technology. Droplet sizes below 200 nm offer properties of transparency, higher penetration on skin, and greater stability than conventional macroemulsions. In O/W systems, we inversely observed oil content and droplet sizes, indicating when oil concentrations are reduced that was desirable to make the best use of surfactants. Excellent stability under 30 day stored centrifuged condition indicated good thermodynamic equilibrium had been achieved, which addressed the typical barriers of natural oil-based cosmetics. Stability was but in part due to unique properties of jojoba oil in synergy with the surfactant system.

4.4 Formulation Development and Practical Applications

The proven success of incorporating micro-emulsion systems into viscous cleansing milk formulations shows the utility of this technology. The incorporation of rheology modifiers (xanthan gum), combined with functional additives, provided products with consumer acceptable sensory attributes while maintaining the nanoscale structure. The skin-compatible pH range (6.5 – 6.8) minimizes the disruption to the skin's natural acid mantle, resolving consumer worries associated with harsh traditional cleansers.

4.5 Sustainability and Commercial Viability

This research adds to the expanding array of literature on sustainable cosmetics as it shows that natural ingredients can be formulated as high-performance products while not compromising efficacy. By using biodegradable surfactants and renewable oil sources, you are meeting consumers' increasing demands for eco-friendly personal care products.

5. CONCLUSION

We developed a new self-emulsifying micro-emulsion-based cleansing milk formulated with jojoba oil and Black seed oil using PEG-40 hydrogenated castor oil as the emulsifier. The systems prepared had size droplets in the nanometric range, excellent thermodynamic stability and had a pH compatible with skin confirming their appropriateness for use in cosmetics. Of all the blends tested Blend A (90:10) had the greatest emulsification capacity and Physicochemical stability, whereas Blend B (80:20) tended to be richer in emollients. The results indicate that by blending natural oils with self-emulsifying systems we can obtain stable, efficacious, and multifunctional cosmetic cleansing formulations.

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